

ANALYTICAL TOOLS USED IN DEVELOPING AN ORGANIZATION'S STRATEGY.**Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna****Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan****Usmanov Shakhzod Shokhrukhovich****2nd year student, group BH-222, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service**

Abstract: This article discusses determining the organization's behavior strategy and implementing this strategy, the internal environment and external environment through strategic management, defining its goals and achieving them.

Keywords: Enterprises, strategy, behavior, management, achievement, market.

In modern Uzbekistan, which has firmly taken the path of a market economy, the role of marketing has increased many times over for activities both within the country and in foreign markets. Therefore, at the present stage, marketing is an important component of the practical activities of Uzbek enterprises. Currently, in all organizations without exception is possible only if the environment allows its implementation. The internal environment of an organization is the source of its lifeblood. It contains the potential that enables an organization to function, and, therefore, to exist and survive in a certain period of time. But the internal environment can also be a source of problems and even the death of an organization if it does not provide the necessary functioning of the organization.

The external environment is the source that supplies the organization with the resources necessary to maintain its internal potential at the proper level. The organization is in a state of constant exchange with the external environment, thereby providing itself with the opportunity to survive. But the resources of the external environment are not limitless. And they are claimed by many other organizations located in the same environment. Therefore, there is always the possibility that the organization will not be able to obtain the necessary resources from the external environment. This can weaken its potential and lead to many negative consequences for the organization. The task of strategic management is to ensure that the organization interacts with its environment in a way that allows it to maintain its potential at the level necessary to achieve its goals and thereby enable it to survive in the long term.

In order to determine the organization's behavioral strategy and implement this strategy, management must have an in-depth understanding of both the internal environment of the organization, its potential and development trends, and the external environment, its development trends and the place occupied by the organization in it. At the same time, both the internal environment and the external environment are studied by strategic management primarily in order to reveal those threats and opportunities that the organization must take into account when defining its goals and achieving them.

Strategic management views the environment as a combination of three environments; the macroenvironment, the immediate environment, and the internal environment.

The macroenvironment creates the general conditions in which an enterprise operates, defining for it and other enterprises the boundaries of what is acceptable and what is unacceptable.

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Just as the atmosphere affects a person differently, the macroenvironment affects an organization to varying degrees depending on its level of “health.”

The macroenvironment in relation to the enterprise is:

1. as a reason and condition for limiting (or expanding) activities;
2. as a prerequisite causing the need for changes in the enterprise.

The cornerstone of analyzing the situation in the industry and competition in it is a thorough study of the competition going on in the industry, identifying its sources and assessing the degree of influence of competitive forces. This step of analysis is especially important because it is impossible to develop a full-fledged strategy without a deep understanding of the nature of competition in the industry.

The analysis of buyers, as components of the immediate environment of the organization, primarily aims to compile a profile of those who buy the product sold by the organization. Studying customers allows an organization to better understand which product will be most accepted by customers, what sales volume the organization can expect, to what extent customers are committed to the product of this particular organization, how much the circle of potential buyers can be expanded, what awaits the product in the future, and much more. .

The analysis of suppliers is aimed at identifying those aspects in the activities of entities that supply the organization with various raw materials, semi-finished products, energy and information resources, finance, etc., on which the efficiency of the organization, the cost and quality of the product produced by the organization depend. Suppliers of materials and components, if they have great power, can make the organization very dependent on themselves. Therefore, when choosing suppliers, it is very important to deeply and comprehensively study their activities and their potential in order to be able to build relationships with them that would provide the organization with maximum strength in interaction with suppliers.

The study of competitors, that is, those with whom the organization has to fight for the resources that it seeks to obtain from the external environment in order to ensure its existence, occupies a special and very important place in strategic management. This study is aimed at identifying the strengths and weaknesses of competitors and, on the basis of this, building your competitive strategy. The competitive environment is formed not only by intra-industry competitors producing similar products and selling them on the same market. Subjects of the competitive environment are also those firms that can enter the market, as well as those firms that produce a substitute product. In addition to them, the organization’s competitive environment is significantly influenced by its buyers and suppliers, who, having bargaining power, can significantly weaken the organization’s position in the competitive field.

Many companies do not pay enough attention to the possible threat from aliens and therefore lose in the competition to those new to their market. It is very important to remember this and create barriers in advance to the entry of potential aliens. Such barriers may be in-depth specialization in the production of a product, low costs due to savings from large production volumes, control over distribution channels, the use of local features that give an advantage in competition, etc. However, any of these measures is effective only when it is a real barrier to the alien. Therefore, it is very important to know well what barriers can stop or prevent a potential newcomer from entering the market and erecting these particular barriers.

Manufacturers of substitute products have very great competitive power. The peculiarity of market transformation in the case of the appearance of a replacement product is that if it has killed

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the market for the old product, then it usually cannot be restored. Therefore, in order to be able to adequately meet the challenge from firms producing a replacement product, the organization must have sufficient potential to move on to creating a new type of product.

Analysis of the labor market is aimed at identifying its potential in providing the organization with the personnel necessary to solve its problems. The organization must study the labor market both from the point of view of the availability of personnel with the required specialty and qualifications, the required level of education, the required age, gender, etc., and from the point of view of the cost of labor. An important area of studying the labor market is the analysis of the policies of trade unions that have influence in this market, since in some cases they can severely limit access to the labor force necessary for the organization.

It is recommended to end the analysis of the external environment by compiling a list of external dangers and opportunities that the organization faces in this environment. The presentation of this list may vary, but, as a rule, it should include weighing factors to rank them according to the degree of impact on the organization and assess the impact. For clarity and to facilitate the work of managers planning the company's strategy, all factors can be placed in two columns: one - opportunity factors, the other - threat factors, arranged in descending order of importance.

Having analyzed the external environment and obtained data on factors that pose threats or provide new opportunities, management must assess whether the firm has the internal strengths to take advantage of opportunities and what internal weaknesses may complicate future problems associated with external threats. This is done by analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the organization. The method used to diagnose internal problems is called management survey. It is based on a comprehensive study of various functional areas of the organization and, depending on the task at hand, can be methodologically simple or more complex. For strategic planning purposes, it is recommended to include five functional areas in the survey - marketing, finance (accounting), production, personnel, as well as organizational culture and image of the organization.

When analyzing the functions of marketing, seven important elements of research are identified:

- market share and competitiveness;
- variety and quality of assortment;
- market demographics;
- market research and development;
- pre-sales and after-sales customer service;
- sales, advertising, product promotion;
- profit.

When analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of an organization, it is necessary to determine the key factors for the company's success.

Key success factors are factors specific to a given industry that bring advantages to it.

Identification of CFUs operating in the near future and identification of the most important ones among them constitute a significant part of the work on strategic planning. A company can gain a competitive advantage by focusing on one or more CFUs.

The result of the analysis of the external and internal environment is the preparation of a SWOT analysis, i.e. identification and assessment of internal weaknesses and strengths, as well as threats and opportunities from the external environment. Both the strengths and weaknesses of a company can have different meanings. Some weaknesses can have a fatal impact on the

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organization, while others will not seriously affect the company or can be easily eliminated. The result of a SWOT analysis should be a predominance of strengths over weaknesses.

The results of this analysis lead to the development of alternative strategies for the operation of the enterprise and a decision on which path the organization's management should direct its activities to achieve the greatest success.

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